

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION INTO CO-BONDED PATCH REPAIRS FOR STRUCTURAL COMPOSITES ADDITIONALLY REINFORCED WITH HIGH PERFORMANCE MULTIFILAMENT YARN

M. Linke¹, M. Moebius¹, F.-D. Georges¹, P. Abel² and T. Gries²

¹Department of Automotive and Aeronautical Engineering, Hamburg University of Applied Sciences
Berliner Tor 9, D-20099 Hamburg, Germany

Email: markus.linke@haw-hamburg.de, web page: <http://www.haw-hamburg.de>

²Institut fuer Textiltechnik Aachen, RWTH Aachen University
Otto-Blumenthal-Str. 1, D-52074 Aachen, Germany

Email: ita@ita.rwth-aachen.de, web page: <http://www.ita.rwth-aachen.de>

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ABSTRACT

Reliable repair of high performance composite structures is still an unsolved issue. This is due to the fact that bonded repairs do not reach the full mechanical strength of the undamaged material and that it is not possible to estimate the residual strength of the joint e.g. through non-destructive testing.

Environmental conditions prevailing during the repair process like humidity or surface contamination play a vital role in establishing a reliable repair. While under laboratory conditions bonded repairs can already reach up to 90 % of the original strength of the component (e.g. stepped single lap joint in tensile testing), those results are generally difficult to achieve under field conditions where unfavourable environmental conditions frequently prevail.

In order to reduce the impact of this issue on the repair performance, a repair method is investigated using high performance multifilament yarns to reinforce the bonding area. The yarns are introduced by sewing the dry textile repair patch to the composite part. The repair patch is impregnated with resin together with the sewing yarn in a resin infusion process thereby co-bonding it to the parent part.

Experimental tests show that the reinforcement by multifilament yarns has the potential to improve the mechanical properties of the repair. However, the structure is also weakened by the drilled holes which are necessary for the connection between plate and dry textile. As both opposing trends determine the mechanical behaviour, the influencing factors have to be known in order to be capable of adequately designing the repair patch.

The parameters with a potential impact on the mechanical behaviour are analysed by experimental and numerical investigations. Experimental tensile tests are performed. The numerical investigations are carried out using the Finite Element Method. The pre-dominant damage phenomena are considered that comprise damage of the composite plate as well as the repair patch, failure of the reinforcement yarns and delamination effects between plate and patch.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) are increasingly used in transportation applications due to their high stiffness to weight as well as strength to weight ratios. They exhibit the potential to contribute significantly to the limitation of the so far continuously growing energy demand of transportation. In civil aviation, carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) are growingly used for primary structures since the 1980s. In the short run, this trend will reach its peak for the aircraft models B787 of Boeing Corporation (Chicago, USA) and A350 XWB of Airbus SA (Toulouse, France) which are built with more than 50 % CFRP based structural components.

Typically, structural components are designed as large and integral structures (like fuselage or wing sections) which cannot be easily replaced. These structures are usually thin-walled complex shaped

shell structures with additional stiffeners like stringers or frames. In aircraft structures, the aerodynamic surface is usually formed by the outer skin of these components, thus making their geometrically accurate smooth surface an integral part of their functionality. In order to ensure an ecological as well as economic advantageous operation of CFRP, it is important that composite structures fulfil further requirements in addition to the mentioned structural ones. One crucial requirement concerns the reparability of FRP components.

Due to the trend towards an increasing use of CFRP components in daily life applications in civil aviation, a higher probability of damages to these structures have to be considered. The replacement of integral CFRP parts like large fuselage sections is cost intensive, time consuming and wastes resources. Therefore, repair concepts for highly stressed structural components made of FRP are necessary enabling the valid, fast and full restoration of the mechanical properties as well as aerodynamic surfaces.

For primary structures, bolted joints are commonly used, in particular for metal structures. The reasoning for that is, among others, concerned with the desired robustness of the repair process and the opportunities to control the repair quality. However, bolted joints add weight to the repaired component, they cannot restore the original aerodynamic surface and typically show a lower joint efficiency in composites than in metals. The latter is due to several reasons. Components made of FRP exhibit e.g. a higher brittleness which leads to little stress relief around the loaded bolt holes. Furthermore, their anisotropy results in higher stress concentration factors. Their susceptibility to delamination effects as well as sensitivity to environmental conditions have to be taken into account, too.

In contrast to bolted joints, bonded repairs show some important advantages concerning structural as well as aerodynamic aspects. They add almost no additional weight to the structure and enable the full restoration of aerodynamic surfaces. Furthermore, the parent material is preserved as far as possible and the connection to the so called repair patch over a large area reduces stress concentrations in the joint [1]. But these advantages are opposed to some deficits that are mainly concerned with the repair process. The repair performance of bonded joints depends on several manufacturing factors. While under laboratory conditions the strength of a bonded repair can be re-established up to 90 % of the undamaged component, the bonded joint strength under field conditions can only reach 60 to 80 % and can vary significantly [2]. As the repair success cannot be checked by non-destructive quality controls, the use of bonded repairs is strongly limited to non-safety critical parts today.

In order to overcome the mentioned shortcomings of bonded joints, the repair process is improved on the one hand. This means that the repair process is automated [3] and improved procedures for surface treatment to enhance the adhesion of the adhesive layer to the mating partners are developed [2]. However, the adhesive interface cannot be checked by non-destructive testing anyway so that the application is limited to damages where the failure of the repair does not endanger the operational safety. On the other hand, the mechanical performance of bonded joints can be improved through reinforcement of the bonding area. Typically, so called z-pins are introduced into the bonding area (see e.g. [4] or [5]) connecting the mating partners after the repair patch is co-bonded to the parent component. Due to assembly reasons, these approaches are usually not suitable [6]. Another repair approach is based on high performance filament yarns instead of z-pins. The yarns are sewed to the parent part through drilled holes thereby connecting the dry repair patch and the parent component. As a consequence, the bonding area is reinforced after both mating partners are co-bonded like it is the case for z-pin reinforcements. However, experimental investigations show contradictory results. Under specific circumstances, this repair approach can significantly improve the repair strength compared to conventional adhesive joints. But it is not absolutely clear under which conditions these strength improvements can be achieved [7].

In order to understand the relevant physical phenomena occurring in bonded joints that are reinforced with multifilament yarns in the bonding area, experimental as well as numerical investigations are carried out. A stepped single lap joint is investigated by varying different joint parameters. The investigations are discussed in the following. First, the repair method is described in general. Secondly, the used specimens are specified. Thirdly, the applied Finite Element (FE-) idealisation is described so that in the subsequent section experimental and numerical results are compared and discussed. This article ends with a conclusion and an outlook to further planned investigations.

2 REPAIR METHOD USING YARNS TO REINFORCE BONDING AREA

The repair method is based on a co-bonding approach (cp. e.g. [6]), i.e. the removed damaged area is filled with dry, uncured textiles (here with non-crimp fabrics, abbreviated NCF) and subsequently cured with the already consolidated parent structure. In contrast to common co-bonded repairs, the bonding area is reinforced with high performance yarns that are stitched through holes to the parent component. A schematic sketch of the repair scheme is shown in Fig. 1 for a single lap joint.

Figure 1: Scheme of a co-bonded repair with additional yarns connecting the repair patch with the cured parent component.

The overall repair process is illustrated in Fig. 2. After damage detection (step 1), the damaged material is milled off ply by ply and the holes for the yarns are drilled so that the final joint geometry is realised concerning the parent part (step 2). Then, the uncured, dry textile is generated matching the ply material as well as the geometry of the parent structure (step 3). Subsequently, the textile repair patch is inserted into the parent structure and fixed with a clamping device (step 4). Afterwards the repair patch is stitched to the parent part through the drilled holes (step 5). Finally, both mating partners are co-bonded in an infusion and curing process (step 6).

Figure 2: Steps of repair procedure: 1) damage detection 2) milling off damaged area ply by ply and drilling holes 3) design of uncured repair patch 4) integration of uncured repair patch and fixing of textile 5) stitching of textile to parent material 6) co-bonding: resin infusion and curing [8].

Concerning the integration of the dry textile patch (step 4), it has to be mentioned that before patch integration is carried out, a surface treatment is commonly performed in order to enhance the bonding performance. Here, no special surface treatment is carried out. The surface is only cleaned using acetone after milling. Samples of textiles stitched to cured parent parts are shown in the Fig. 3a and 3b.

Manufactured single lap joints are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 3: Uncured repair patch samples consisting of stitched NCF and cured parent part: a) CFRP parent structure combined with NCF by glass and carbon yarns b) repair patch based on glass fibre NCF stitched by carbon yarn to glass fibre reinforced plastic parent structure [8].

Figure 4: Manufactured single lap joint made of glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) and reinforced with carbon yarns [8].

3 DEFINITION OF SPECIMENS

There are two different types of parent components that are used for the study. This comprises a glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP-) and a CFRP-laminate. The test specimens are defined in the following for each laminate. In general, three different types of specimens are considered per laminate. An undamaged parent component (called reference specimen), a conventional co-bonded stepped single lap joint (called co-bond specimen) and a single lap joint reinforced with different yarns (called reinforced specimen).

3.1 GFRP-Laminates

There are four different specimens based on glass fibre NCF investigated under tensile testing here. This comprises unrepaired specimens (called G-reference), co-bonded stepped single lap joints (called G-co-bond) and co-bonded stepped single lap joints with additional reinforcement of the bonding area using high performance yarns. If the yarn is made of glass fibre (GF) resp. carbon fibre (CF), we reference them by G-GF-reinforced resp. G-CF-reinforced. The geometry of the specimens is defined in Fig. 5.

The laminate consists of four bi-axial NCF built up by glass fibre PPG 2002 1200 tex in 0° -direction (336 g/m^2) and PPG 2001 600 tex in 90° -direction (288 g/m^2) according to [9]. The layer set-up is defined in the through-thickness direction (here positive z-direction) starting at the bottom layer according to Fig. 5. The layer set-up is $(0^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ, 0^\circ)_{\text{symmetric}}$ for all GFRP-specimens. The resin RIM135 is used [10]. The layer thicknesses are not available. They can be computed based on mean

values of the sectional area considering a density of 2.55 g/cm³ for glass fibres. As a result, they differ between each sample. The resulting thicknesses of the 0°- and 90°-layers, the total thickness as well as the fibre volume content are specified in Tab. 1. The calculated fibre volume content ranges from 45 to 47 %. The yarn density of the glass fibre amounts to 408 tex and the one of the carbon fibre to 400 tex. The diameter of the drilled holes is 1 mm.

Figure 5: Geometry of single lap joints made of GFRP parent material.

Table 1: Definition of GFRP-specimens.

Specimen	layer thickness [mm]		t [mm]	thickness [mm]	fiber volume content [-]
	0°-ply	90°-ply			
G-reference	0.285	0.245	0.530	2.121	0.462
G-co-bond	0.281	0.241	0.523	2.090	0.468
G-GF-reinforced	0.288	0.247	0.535	2.139	0.458
G-CF-reinforced	0.283	0.243	0.526	2.102	0.466

3.2 CFRP-Laminates

The notation of the CFRP-specimens is chosen in the way like it is the case for the GFRP-specimens according to subsection 3.1. Therefore, the undamaged specimens are called C-reference and the co-bonded stepped single lap joints C-co-bond. The co-bonded stepped single lap joints with additional yarn reinforcement are defined by C-GF-reinforced resp. C-CF-reinforced if the yarn is made of glass resp. carbon fibre. The geometry of the specimens is defined in Fig. 6.

The laminate is made of 6 layers of bi-axial NCF with an area weight of 304 g/m² (according to information given in [9]). The layer set-up is defined in the through-thickness direction (here positive z-direction) starting at the bottom layer according to Fig. 6. The layer set-up is (90°, 0°, 0°, 90°, 90°, 0°)_{symmetric} for all CFRP-specimens. The resin is the same as it is the case for the GFRP-laminates. The layer thicknesses are derived by using the measured values of the sectional area. A density of 1.80 g/cm³ is assumed for carbon fibres. The resulting layer thicknesses, the total thickness as well as the fibre volume content are specified in Tab. 2. The same yarns for reinforcement are applied as for CFRP-laminates.

Figure 6: Geometry of single lap joints made of CFRP parent material.

Table 2: Definition of CFRP-specimens.

Specimen	0°- and 90°-ply thickness [mm]	t [mm]	thickness [mm]	fiber volume content [-]
C-reference	0.173	0.347	2.080	0.487
C-co-bond	0.193	0.385	2.310	0.439
C-GF-reinforced	0.203	0.405	2.430	0.417
C-CF-reinforced	0.202	0.403	2.420	0.419

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

The Finite Element Method (FEM-) code Abaqus/Explicit Version 6-11.2 (Dassault Systèmes SA, France) is used.

The laminates are idealised based on a unidirectional (UD-) layer formulation where the linear-elastic material characteristics are calculated using Puck's rule of mixture [11]. It is assumed that the fibres are perfectly aligned in the 0°-direction and that the fibre volume content is adequately approximated according to section 3. Each layer of the laminate is modelled based on a quadrilateral solid shell formulation (element type SC8R according to [12]) leading to the consideration of the in-plane material characteristics. Each ply is modelled with one element in the through-thickness direction. Failure of the UD-layers is considered using Hashin's composite model with respect to [13].

Concerning the GFRP-specimens, the failure stresses are determined based on [14] where composites with similar NCF and resin are analysed in detail. The characteristic values are computed by considering the actual fibre content volume accordingly and calibrating them with available tensile tests of the undamaged parent component. The latter test specimens are generally called here reference specimens (cp. GFRP- as well as CFRP-specimen definition in section 3). Element deletion is considered if all failure modes are fully reached.

Concerning the CFRP-specimens, the failure stresses are derived using [15] and the computed fibre volume content. Furthermore, model calibration is applied using experimental results of

reference specimens. The FE idealisation equals the one of the GFRP-specimens.

The reinforcing yarns are idealised by 8-node linear brick elements (solid element type C3D8 according to [12]) with an ideal elastic-plastic stress-strain relationship using v. Mises equivalent stress formulation. Element damage and element deletion are considered. The linear-elastic material characteristics in the yarn direction are calculated by Puck's rule of mixture [11]. The fibre volume content is determined by the diameter of the drilled holes in the parent structure and by the yarn as well as fibre densities given in section 3. Due to simplicity reasons, only the yarn in the holes is idealised but the yarn pattern on the surface of the specimen is not modelled here.

The co-bonded area between the mating partners is idealised with 8-node three-dimensional cohesive elements (element type COH3D8 according to [12]). It is a cohesive element formulation using a traction-separation response. The element thickness amounts to 0.05 mm. The damage is initiated based on a maximum nominal stress criterion. Complete element degradation is considered but no element deletion.

The boundary conditions are applied with a rigid tie (coupling constraint with a surface-based coupling definition according to [12]) linked to the sectional areas at the ends of the specimens. On one edge, all degrees of freedom are fixed, on the other edge, all degrees of freedom are clamped except the longitudinal displacement which is prescribed as desired.

In order to reduce the computational effort, only one-fifth of each specimen is modelled containing one yarn row in the longitudinal direction. The meshes are selected problem dependent and are based on limited mesh sensitivity analyses as well as overall available computational resources. Furthermore, due to the highly dynamic fracture process, an automated mass scaling approach is applied.

5 RESULTS

The experimental testing is carried out using a standard tensile testing device (Z250 of Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany). The actual geometry and the deformation pattern are measured using an optical 3D analysis system (ARAMIS system of GOM mbH, Braunschweig, Germany) which is aligned by strain gauge measuring. Overall stresses are calculated based on the measured tension forces (given by tensile testing device) and the section area (given by ARAMIS system) as well as by the ARAMIS system itself. In general, five specimens were tested per sample. The FEM analyses are performed using the modeling approach and code according to section 4.

5.1 Experimental testing and FEM-simulation

The comparison between the experimental results and the FEM computations concerning GFRP-laminates are shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that the strength of the co-bonded joint (G-co-bond) is improved due to the yarn reinforcement by about 5 % for a glass yarn (G-GF-reinforced) and by about 13 % for a carbon yarn (G-CF-reinforced). Furthermore, the modeling approach leads to a very good agreement of the experimental results with the FEM simulation. The FEM analyses show deviations clearly below 5 % with respect to the mean experimental value. This result is completely within the range of the experimental root mean square deviation. The nominal stress versus strain curve is exemplarily illustrated in Fig. 8 for the sample G-CF-reinforced showing good agreement also for the stress-strain trend.

Concerning CFRP joint samples, we cannot observe an increase of the joint performance due to the application of yarn reinforcements (cp. experimental results in Fig. 9) as it is the case for GFRP samples. The joints with yarn reinforcement (C-GF-reinforced as well as C-CF-reinforced) show generally the same tensile strength like the joints without any reinforcement (C-co-bond). Moreover, no significant difference is observed for different yarn types. Again, the experimental results and the FEM computations are in good agreement. A larger deviation of about 9 % is only observed between experimental testing and FEM-simulation for the specimens C-GF-reinforced.

Figure 7: Tensile joint strength of GFRP-laminates.

Figure 8: Nominal stress versus strain curve for joint samples G-CF-reinforced.

Figure 9: Tensile joint strength of CFRP-laminates.

5.2 Parameters with effect on joint performance

The derived FE models are used to estimate potential parameters with an impact on the joint performance. Here, the yarn density as well as the diameter of the drilled yarn holes are discussed.

As the yarn material characteristics have an impact on the fracture mechanics of the bonding area, the yarn density is increased from the experimental set-up, i.e. the fibre volume content φ is increased in three steps. All other values are kept constant. First, a yarn twice as strong as the original one is used. The maximum theoretically possible fibre volume content for quadratic as well as hexagonal fibre packing ($\varphi \approx 79\%$ resp. 91%) is then considered in order to estimate the absolute potential of improving the bonding between the mating partners due to the yarn. The simulation results are shown in Fig. 10 for the specimens C-CF-reinforced. The maximum tensile strength is compared to the experimental result of the parent material (C-reference). A doubled yarn density ($\varphi = 56\%$) leads to an improvement of about 9 percentage points. The absolute performance rise seems to be limited by about 17 percentage points which we observe for theoretical maximum yarn packing within the yarn holes. Concerning these results, it has to be kept in mind, however, that the physical fracture mechanisms of the yarn are idealized in a simple way based on an isotropic hardening rule for the yarn.

Drilling holes into the parent material leads to a strength reduction due to a decrease of the area carrying the load, among others. In order to estimate the effect of the hole on the strength, a reduction of the hole diameter is investigated simultaneously using the same yarn. The diameter is reduced in such a manner that the fibre volume content in the hole equals the ones selected for the aforementioned analyses concerning an increase of the yarn density, i.e. starting from a fibre volume content of $\varphi = 28\%$ for a hole with diameter 1 mm, it is increased over 56% to 79% resp. 91% (for quadratic resp. hexagonal fibre packing). The simulation results are illustrated in Fig. 11 for the specimens C-CF-reinforced.

Figure 10: Estimated achievable joint performance for specimens C-CF-reinforced if the yarn hole diameter is kept constant and the fibre volume content is increased.

Figure 11: Estimated achievable joint performance for specimens C-CF-reinforced if the yarn hole diameter is reduced in such a way that specific fibre contents are reached (applied yarn is the same).

7 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Experimental and numerical investigations of co-bonded joints with additional yarn reinforcement in the bonding area are illustrated. The experimental results show that a yarn reinforcement of the bonding area exhibits the potential to improve the joint performance in tensile loading. However, this improvement is not observed for all selected joint parameters. Therefore, numerical studies are carried out based on FE-idealizations enabling the systematic variation of joint parameters. The established FE-models show good agreement with the performed experimental tests. The numerical studies considering different joint parameters suggest that the reinforcement is probably most effective if the joint failure is dominated by the delamination of the bonding area. However, this reasoning has to be checked further as the FE-yarn modelling is based on a simple nonlinear isotropic material law. Therefore, the FE-yarn idealization will be improved to consider a wider range of fibre reinforced failure mechanisms. This work also comes along with additional experimental testing. Consequently, the FE-models as well as the derived findings can be validated for a wider range of parameters.

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